

Inequality leads to the evolution of intolerance in reputation-based populations

Luis A. Martinez-Vaquero^{1, 2, 3, a)}

¹⁾ *Grupo de Sistemas Complejos, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, 28040 Madrid, Spain*

²⁾ *DEFE, Escuela Técnica Superior de Arquitectura, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, 28040 Madrid, Spain*

³⁾ *Grupo Interdisciplinar de Sistemas Complejos, Universidad Carlos III de Madrid, 28911 Leganés, Madrid, Spain*

(Dated: 23 January 2023)

This work studies the impact of economic inequality on the evolution of intolerance through a reputation-based model of indirect reciprocity. Results show that economic inequality is a powerful enhancer of intolerance, inducing the escalation of out-group discrimination even without the presence of new intolerant mutants. It also generates behavior modifications within tolerant disfavored minorities: their members either relax punishments against the uncooperative or prioritize helping the wealthy, even suffering discrimination in return. On the other hand, the redistribution of wealth is proved as a viable solution to avoid the spread of intolerance as long as it increases equality and is implemented before intolerance permeates part of the population.

Economic inequality has been rising in modern societies during the last years and, according to evidence, it could be a key factor behind intolerance outbreaks. As our societies become more dependent on public reputation systems, a deeper understanding of the relationship between inequality, intolerance, and reputation is required. Evolutionary game theory has been proved as a suitable methodology to study the emergence and evolution of cooperation in populations. One of the main mechanisms proposed to explain cooperative behaviors in this framework is indirect reciprocity, which relies on the assignment of reputations to decide whether to cooperate with the other. Adapting an indirect reciprocity model to incorporate economic inequality and intolerance, this work studies the impact of the former on the emergence of the latter. It is analyzed under what circumstances intolerant strategies could invade tolerant groups in different scenarios and what is required for tolerance to be restored. Results show that inequality triggers the escalation of discriminatory attitudes at different levels. However, it is also responsible of counterintuitive behaviors within tolerant groups. One of the most significant is that tolerant disfavored minorities may prioritize helping wealthy individuals who discriminate against over their own kind. The model is also applied to study the conditions under which the redistribution of wealth may become a feasible solution to avoid intolerance. Results show that this policy should guarantee the reduction of inequality and be implemented before intolerant individuals invade any group of the

population.

I. INTRODUCTION

The evolution of inequality from small-scale egalitarian societies was a major transition in human social organization. It emerged in Holocene, when resources became predictable and followed gradient or patching distributions¹. During the last decades, economic inequality has been decreasing among nations through the improvement of low-income countries' economies. However, the picture within nations is pretty different: the gaps between higher and lower income economic classes have been continuously growing². Some authors argued that globalization has been one of the main catalysers of inequality³. Modern democracies have seen how their income inequality has skyrocketed in recent decades⁴⁻⁷. Even European countries, which have developed policies orientated to ensure a fairer share of the economic growth among the low level income groups, have failed to achieve the inequality reduction United Nations Sustainable Development Goal⁸. Moreover, national average income levels have shown not to be good proxies of inequality for most countries since some high- or middle-income countries display extreme inequality levels, such as Brazil, India and China⁹.

On the other hand, discriminatory behaviors are relatively common in heterogeneous societies where individuals tend to form differentiated groups¹⁰⁻¹³. Discrimination usually comes in two different flavours¹⁴: intolerance against individuals from other groups¹⁵⁻¹⁷ and favoritism toward same group individuals¹⁸⁻²⁰. Intolerance can be materialized through many different discriminatory behaviors, mainly related to ethnicity, gender, age, sexual preferences, religion and nationality²¹⁻²⁵. Despite the

^{a)}l.martinez.vaquero@upm.es

TABLE I. Summary of the main magnitudes used in the model.

Magnitude	Description
b	Benefit of receiving help.
c	Cost of helping.
$a_{\alpha,\beta}$	Action rule: decision of a donor with reputation α on helping or not a recipient with reputation β .
$m_{\alpha,\beta}(a)$	Moral assessment: new reputation assigned to an individual with reputation α which has performed an action a on an individual with reputation β .
y	Fraction of individuals belonging to subpopulation A.
ϵ_X	Economic stress of subpopulation X .
ϵ	Global economic stress.
G	Gini coefficient.
$\eta_{X,Y}$	Intention of cooperation of individuals from subpopulation X over individuals from subpopulation Y .
$\theta_{X,Y}$	Probability that a X -strategist helps a Y -strategist.
W_i	Average payoff that i -individuals receive.
$x_i^{\Lambda_A \Lambda_B \Lambda_M}$	Fraction of i -individuals with reputations Λ_A , Λ_B , and Λ_M assigned by A-residents, B-residents, and mutants.

fact that the relationship between economic income has been extensively discussed and analyzed^{26–32}, some evidences indicate that economic inequality may be at least as important as the absolute economic income in social trust and tolerance^{33–37}.

Previous theoretical works have shown that discriminatory behaviors can evolutionarily emerge in the framework of indirect reciprocity^{38–41} and, more specifically, they can outbreak more easily under global economic stress especially among minorities in reputation-based populations⁴². Indirect reciprocity^{43,44} is one of the main mechanisms proposed to explain the evolution of cooperation under the evolutionary game theory framework^{45–50}, demonstrating its relevance in human societies^{51–56}. Contrary to direct reciprocity⁵⁷, where individuals react to their partners' previous actions, indirect reciprocity involves a third party. There exist different variants of indirect reciprocity^{46,58}, however the most prevalent is based on reputation^{45,49,52,59–61}. Individuals judge others by assigning them reputations based on the actions they witness, which in turn influence decisions in future encounters. The emergence of moral assessments is an interesting consequence of these models which have received significant attention in the literature^{59,62,63}, making them suitable to study the conditions under which intolerant behaviors can appear and spread in a population. Traditionally, the importance of reputation mechanisms was restricted mainly to small-scale societies, however, as a result of the proliferation of public online reputation-based systems, it influences decisions at all scale levels in current societies^{64,65}.

Despite all this progress, the role of inequality still remains unclear in the evolutionary emergence of intolerance in general and in reputation-based societies in particular. The present work proposes an evolutionary game theoretical model based on indirect reciprocity where inequality is incorporated considering different groups with different economic levels. This allows to study how in-

equality impacts the intention of cooperation within and across groups and how it shapes the evolution of intolerant behaviors. It is also analyzed under what conditions the redistribution of wealth may become a potential solution to contain the emergence of intolerance.

II. MODEL

The model proposed in this work is built upon previous reputation-based models of indirect reciprocity^{42,60} to account for the effect of group economic inequality on the emergence of intolerance. Table I summarizes the main magnitudes used in this model. It is assumed an infinitely large, well-mixed population of individuals who randomly interact in pairs, involving a *donor* and a *recipient*. The donor can either help the recipient (C from *cooperate*), giving an amount b at a personal cost c ($b > c$), or fail to do it (D from *defect*). The whole population witness the action performed, and each individual judges this action either as *good* (G) or as *bad* (B), updating the donor's reputation if necessary. Therefore everyone in the population has an opinion regarding every other one's attitudes. Assuming third-order strategies, the donor's decision to help or not to help the recipient depends on her reputation α , and the reputation of the recipient β (both judged from the viewpoint of the donor) according to *action rules* $a_{\alpha\beta}$. Furthermore, every individual judges any action witnessed a according to *moral assessments* $m_{\alpha\beta}(a)$, which involves the reputations of the donor and the recipient (from the viewpoint of the witness) and the action performed. Pairwise interactions between members of the population continue to happen indefinitely. Thus, individuals' payoffs are computed as the average payoffs of all interactions they are involved in once the equilibrium of the dynamics is reached.

The emergence of intolerance is allowed by dividing the population into two different groups: a group A with

y fraction of individuals and a group B with $1 - y$ individuals. According to their behavior toward the other group, individuals can be classified as tolerant or intolerant. Tolerant individuals always stick to the chosen strategy ignoring individuals' groups—they help or not, or judge, as if everyone belonged to the same group. Intolerant individuals, on the contrary, always assign bad reputation to individuals from the opposite group and refuse to help them; they also assign bad (good) reputation to anyone who helps (refuses to help) someone from the opposite group. Other than that, all individuals in the population share the same action rules and moral assessments.

The model introduces economic stress by limiting individuals' resources imposing a fraction of failed assistances, which is referred to in the literature as *action error*^{47,48,59,66,67}. In order to analyze how economic inequality affects the spread of intolerance, A and B individuals are allowed to undergo different levels of economic stress ϵ_A and ϵ_B , respectively. The standard index to measure economic inequality is the Gini coefficient⁶⁸. For a population with two levels of income, it is simply defined as the difference between the fraction of income of the wealthiest subpopulation, minus the fraction of the total population that correspond to the wealthiest people. Taking as reference subpopulation A, and ϵ_X being the economic stress of subpopulation X, it is reasonable to assume that subpopulation A's income is proportional to $y(1 - \epsilon_A)$, and that the global income is $1 - \epsilon = y(1 - \epsilon_A) + (1 - y)(1 - \epsilon_B)$. Hence the Gini coefficient becomes

$$G = \frac{y(1 - y)}{1 - \epsilon} (\epsilon_B - \epsilon_A) \quad (1)$$

The value of the economic stress of each subpopulation can be recovered from the Gini coefficient for a given global economic stress ϵ :

$$\epsilon_A = \epsilon - \frac{1 - \epsilon}{y} G \quad (2)$$

$$\epsilon_B = \epsilon + \frac{1 - \epsilon}{1 - y} G \quad (3)$$

Thanks to this artefact it is easy to interpret the meaning of increasing or decreasing G either way. The higher the absolute value of G , the more unequal the population in favor of subpopulation A ($G > 0$) or subpopulation B ($G < 0$).

Among all possible strategies—combinations of action rules and moral assessments—the so-called *leading eight strategies* (see Table II) were proved evolutionarily stable, obtain significantly high payoffs, promote cooperation and are robust against errors and cheating^{59,63}. For each of the leading eight strategies, it was analyzed the range of parameters for which different invasions may succeed (see next sections for details). The different invasion scenarios are represented in Fig. 1 and denoted $S_M|S_A S_B$ or

FIG. 1. Conceptual representation of the four possible invasions analyzed: intolerance invading a tolerant group in fully tolerant population (I|TT), tolerance invading an intolerant group with other group remaining tolerant (T|IT), intolerance invading a tolerant group in a population where the other group has already become intolerant (IT|I), and tolerance invading a intolerant group in a fully intolerant population (T|II).

$S_A S_B | S_M$, depending on whether it is the A or the B subpopulation that is being invaded by mutants M, respectively, where S_i can take the values T (tolerant strategy) or I (intolerant strategy). Thus, e.g., I|TT means that intolerant mutants are attempting to invade the A subpopulation of a fully tolerant population; or TI|T means that tolerant mutants are attempting to invade the B subpopulation of a population formed by A tolerant individuals and B intolerant individuals. The leading eight strategies are usually classified in three groups (see Table II) according to their stability against invasions by free-riders⁵⁹. Since it has already been shown that strategies of the same group behave similarly and strategies of group **III** resist invasions by intolerant strategies under any circumstance⁴², most results displayed from now on will refer to one representative strategy of each group **I** and **II**.

A. Evolutionary stability

Each invasion scenario analyzed consists of a resident population and a small fraction of mutant individuals that try to invade one of the subpopulations. Resident populations are prepared by making all combinations of A tolerant/intolerant individuals with B tolerant/intolerant ones; mutants exhibit the opposite (in)tolerant behavior of the subpopulation they are attempting to invade. Only the onset of the invasion is determined, but not the final composition of the population. Finding whether the invading strategy replaces the resident population or end up coexisting with it is a much more complex problem⁴² and is beyond the scope of this work.

A strategy is evolutionarily stable if a population fully formed by individuals who play that strategy can resist the invasion of a small fraction of mutants that play other strategies⁶⁹. Assuming a population formed by A-type

TABLE II. Leading eight strategies. Moral assessments $m_{\alpha\beta}(a)$ and action rules $a_{\alpha\beta}$ for third-order indirect reciprocity strategies that are evolutionarily stable and obtain high payoff when in homogeneous populations. Strategies are arranged in three different groups according with their similar behavior. Strategies in bold are used as representatives of each group for subsequent analysis.

	$m_{GG}(C)$	$m_{GG}(D)$	$m_{GB}(C)$	$m_{GB}(D)$	$m_{BG}(C)$	$m_{BG}(D)$	$m_{BB}(C)$	$m_{BB}(D)$	a_{GG}	a_{GB}	a_{BG}	a_{BB}
I	G	B	B	G	G	B	G	B	C	D	C	C
	G	B	G	G	G	B	G	B	C	D	C	C
II	G	B	G	G	G	B	B	G	C	D	C	D
	G	B	G	G	G	B	G	G	C	D	C	D
	G	B	B	G	G	B	G	G	C	D	C	D
III	G	B	G	G	G	B	B	B	C	D	C	D
	G	B	B	G	G	B	B	B	C	D	C	D

and B-type residents, the condition for the former to resist the invasion of mutants that play a different strategy is $W_A > W_M$, where W_A and W_M are the average payoffs received by A-type residents and by mutants, respectively. They can be obtained as

$$W_A = b[y\theta_{A,A} + (1-y)\theta_{B,A}] - c[y\theta_{A,A} + (1-y)\theta_{A,B}], \quad (4)$$

$$W_M = b[y\theta_{A,M} + (1-y)\theta_{B,M}] - c[y\theta_{M,A} + (1-y)\theta_{M,B}], \quad (5)$$

where $\theta_{X,Y} = (1 - \epsilon_X)\eta_{X,Y}$ is the probability that a X-strategist helps a Y-strategist. The intention of cooperation $\eta_{X,Y} = 0$ if the X-strategist is intolerant and $X \neq Y$, and

$$\eta_{X,Y} = \sum_{\alpha\beta} \chi_\alpha(g_X^X) \chi_\beta(g_Y^X) a_{\alpha\beta} \quad (6)$$

otherwise, where g_i^j is the fraction of i -strategists that are considered good by j -strategists and $\chi_\gamma(x) = \gamma x + (1 - \gamma)(1 - x)$. In the case where mutants attempt to invade the B subpopulation, B-type residents resist the invasion if $W_B > W_M$ interchanging subscript A by B and y by $1 - y$ in Eqs. 4 and 5:

$$W_B = b[(1-y)\theta_{B,B} + y\theta_{A,B}] - c[(1-y)\theta_{B,B} + y\theta_{B,A}], \quad (7)$$

$$W_M = b[(1-y)\theta_{B,M} + y\theta_{A,M}] - c[(1-y)\theta_{M,B} + y\theta_{M,A}], \quad (8)$$

B. Reputation dynamics

Defining $x_i^{\Lambda_A \Lambda_B \Lambda_M}$ as the fractions of i -individuals with reputations Λ_A , Λ_B , and Λ_M assigned by A-residents, B-residents, and mutants, respectively, fractions g_i^j can be expressed as

$$g_i^A = x_i^{G^{**}}, \quad g_i^B = x_i^{*G^*}, \quad g_i^M = x_i^{**G}, \quad (9)$$

where the superscript * stands for *any reputation*. For instance, $x_i^{G^{**}} = \sum_{\Lambda_B} \sum_{\Lambda_M} x_i^{G \Lambda_B \Lambda_M}$. In practice, only a few of these fractions are necessary to compute the different g_i^j . Since mutants appear in a very low rate, donors only interact with residents. Under this approximation, the dynamics of the fractions of residents are reduced to

$$\dot{x}_A^{\Lambda_A \Lambda_M} = y T_{A,A}^{\Lambda_A \Lambda_M} + (1-y) F_{A,B}^{\Lambda_A \Lambda_M} - x_A^{\Lambda_A \Lambda_M}, \quad (10)$$

$$\dot{x}_A^{\Lambda_A \Lambda_B^*} = y T_{A,A}^{\Lambda_A \Lambda_B^*} + (1-y) F_{A,B}^{\Lambda_A \Lambda_B^*} - x_A^{\Lambda_A \Lambda_B^*}, \quad (11)$$

$$\dot{x}_B^{\Lambda_A \Lambda_B^*} = y F_{B,A}^{\Lambda_A \Lambda_B^*} + (1-y) T_{B,B}^{\Lambda_A \Lambda_B^*} - x_B^{\Lambda_A \Lambda_B^*}, \quad (12)$$

$$\dot{x}_B^{*\Lambda_B \Lambda_M} = y F_{B,A}^{\Lambda_B \Lambda_M} + (1-y) T_{B,B}^{\Lambda_B \Lambda_M} - x_B^{*\Lambda_B \Lambda_M}, \quad (13)$$

and are decoupled from the equations that governs the dynamics of the mutants, which are given by:

$$\dot{x}_M^{\Lambda_A \Lambda_M} = y T_{M,A}^{\Lambda_A \Lambda_M} + (1-y) F_{M,B}^{\Lambda_A \Lambda_M} - x_M^{\Lambda_A \Lambda_M}, \quad (14)$$

$$\dot{x}_M^{*\Lambda_B \Lambda_M} = y F_{M,A}^{\Lambda_B \Lambda_M} + (1-y) T_{M,B}^{\Lambda_B \Lambda_M} - x_M^{*\Lambda_B \Lambda_M} \quad (15)$$

in the case of A-type and B-type mutants, respectively. In previous Eqs. 10–15, the interactions with recipients of the same and of the opposite group have been split into $T_{i,j}^{\Lambda_i \Lambda_m}$ and $F_{i,j}^{\Lambda_i \Lambda_m}$, respectively. Fractions $T_{i,j}^{\Lambda_i \Lambda_m}$ are common for all invasion scenarios whereas $F_{i,j}^{\Lambda_i \Lambda_m}$ depend on the specific scenario. These fractions together with other further simplifications and the processes to complete calculations are detailed in Appendix.

III. RESULTS

A. Intention of cooperation

The study of the cooperation level as a function of inequality under different configurations provides first insights on why intolerance can or cannot outbreak in fragmented societies. Specifically, it will be focused on the intention of cooperation, which is the probability that an individual from subpopulation X *intends* to cooperate with an individual from subpopulation Y according only to her strategy. This magnitude is more adequate to infer

FIG. 2. Intention of cooperation under inequality. Intention of cooperation level of subpopulations X with subpopulations Y ($X \rightarrow Y$) as a function of the Gini coefficient for a completely tolerant population (TT) and a population where A-individuals became intolerant (IT). Intention of cooperation levels are grouped according to in-group (first row) and out-group (second row) behavior criteria. Total intention of cooperation for each subpopulation and the population as a whole is also shown (third row). Results for different subpopulation sizes and strategies are displayed. Empty circles in the legend stand for cases where the intention of cooperation is always zero, and vertical grey lines mark equality ($G = 0$). Global economic stress $\epsilon = 0.3$.

the actual individuals' intentions regardless of their resource limitations. Note that economic stress still has an important impact on the intention of cooperation since it influences individuals' reputations, which are based on others' actual actions. In order to study the influence of inequality on the intention of cooperation, the global wealth of the population is fixed to $\epsilon = y\epsilon_A + (1-y)\epsilon_B$. Two scenarios will be analyzed: a completely tolerant resident population (TT) and a population where intolerance has taken over subpopulation A (IT), i.e., the scenarios before and after a potential success of an I|TT invasion.

Figure 2 shows the intention of cooperation of individuals from each subpopulation as a function of the Gini coefficient for different compositions of the population. Interactions are grouped in in-group and out-group behaviors, i.e., individuals interacting with members of their own and of the other subpopulation, respectively. The total intention of cooperation for each subpopulation and for the population as a whole is also presented. Results for other parameters values and strategies are displayed in Supplementary Figs. S1-S6.

From the very definition of the model, it was already known that there exists a general symmetry in the TT scenario, such that results should no be altered by exchanging y for $1-y$ and A for B, as it is confirmed in Fig. 2. As expected, total cooperation levels of intolerant individuals are lower than those of the tolerant ones, mainly because they never cooperate with members of the other subpopulation. By extension, the aggregate cooperation level in TT scenario is always higher than in the IT scenario.

Results begin to be more interesting when observing the specific behavior between certain subpopulations. In general, intolerant mutant individuals who initially appear in tolerant populations ($A_M \rightarrow A$ in scenario TT) display significant lower cooperation levels than their tolerant counterparts even with their own kind ($A \rightarrow A$ in scenario TT) since they punish them for helping individuals from the other group. However, when these intolerant individuals settle ($A \rightarrow A$ in scenario IT), they become more cooperative with their kind than the tolerant individuals they replace ($A \rightarrow A$ in scenario TT). On the other hand, individuals that remain tolerant reduce

FIG. 3. Invasion of intolerance for strategy I. Different regions of the ϵ_A - ϵ_B plane where invasions I|TT (blue), T|IT (red) and T|IT (yellow) are successful for strategy I and different fractions of subpopulation A. Overlaps are colored with the corresponding mixed color (the key is provided by the overlapping circles). Grey continuous lines correspond to constant global economic stress $\epsilon = y\epsilon_A + (1-y)\epsilon_B$. Gini coefficient changes moving along these lines from $G = 0$ on the diagonal $\epsilon_A = \epsilon_B$ (dotted lines) to $G > 0$ below it (favoring subpopulation A) or to $G < 0$ above it (favoring subpopulation B). Benefit-to-cost ratio $b/c = 2$.

their intention of cooperation toward those that become intolerant (B→A in scenarios TT and IT). This change is amplified when tolerant constitute a disfavored majority ($y < 0.5$ and $G > 0$) and reduced when they belong to a disfavored minority ($y > 0.5$ and $G > 0$).

The main differences between strategies I and II are related to the in-group behavior of tolerant minority subpopulations —A when $y < 0.5$ in TT and B when $y > 0.5$ in both TT and IT scenarios. The more disfavored these subpopulations are ($G < 0$ for A, and $G > 0$ for B), the less they intend to cooperate with their kind when following strategy II (linear relationship between intention of cooperation and G). This attitude makes them more cooperative with wealthier individuals, even if the latter are intolerant against them (B→A in scenario IT), than with their own group (B→B in scenario IT) under disfavored economic conditions (high value of G). On the other hand, individuals following strategy I display a threshold of G from which they begin to increase their intention of cooperation level. In other words, strategy I tolerant individuals exhibit the highest intention of cooperation toward their own subgroup when their economic conditions are extreme.

For instance, when $y = 0.7$ and $G = 0.3$, B individuals following strategy II cooperate about three times more with A intolerant individuals than with their own, whereas if they follow strategy I they maintain the maximum level of cooperation regardless of the recipient. This

difference leads to another one: The total intention of cooperation of individuals that play strategy II in tolerant populations is not affected by inequality and is the same no matter if they are in the minority or in the majority. Contrarily, strategy I individuals display higher total intention of cooperation when they belong to the disfavored minority. According to how strategies of groups I and II are defined, one can see that the only difference between them is how individuals that recognise themselves as bad should act when encountering other individuals also with bad reputation (a_{BB}). Strategists playing I intend to cooperate whereas strategists playing II defect. Moral assessments $m_{BB}(C)$ and $m_{BB}(D)$, respectively, are coherent with these actions assigning a good reputation to the donor after these behaviors. Therefore strategy I adopts a relax demeanour when both actors have bad reputation, increasing cooperation when bad economic conditions do not easily allow it, whereas strategy II is more strict punishing defections.

Results for strategy III are shown in Supplementary Figs. S5 and S6 for completeness. Strategies III display behaviors similar to those from group II. The main quantitative difference is that the former display lower cooperation levels, which is especially significant for tolerant B subpopulation, which more often refuses to help intolerant individuals (IT scenario), except if a high inequality disfavored them. On the other hand, the behavior of this B tolerant subpopulation with its kind is not affected by

FIG. 4. Invasion of intolerance for strategy II. Notation and color criteria follow the same as in Fig. 3.

A becoming intolerant. These attitudes make strategies **III** more resistant to the invasion of intolerance.

Increasing the global economic stress ϵ (Supplementary Figs. S1-S6) does not show a substantial effect on individual behavior beyond reducing cooperation levels—defection even unintentional usually brings bad reputation. The only exception is mutant intolerant individuals: under some conditions they increase its in-group cooperation level because they see with better eyes their kind not cooperating with the other group, which happens more frequently when global economic stress is higher.

B. Emergence of intolerance

The next natural step is to analyze under which conditions a small fraction of intolerant (tolerant) mutants can invade a tolerant (intolerant) resident subpopulation. Figures 3 and 4 represent the parameter regions where each one of the different invasions succeeds in a ϵ_B - ϵ_A plane for a given composition of the population y . For the sake of clarity, the analysis starts by considering the I|TT scenario, i.e., intolerant mutants try to invade subpopulation A of a fully tolerant population. Next it is studied whether tolerance can be restored provided the first invasion had spread all over subpopulation A (T|IT scenario), as well as if intolerant mutants can also invade subpopulation B (IT|I scenario). The invasion of tolerant mutants of a fully intolerant population (T|II or II|T) does not succeed for any combination of parameters and then it is not represented. All the displayed results have been obtained for a benefit-to-cost ratio $b/c = 2$; it was already proved⁴² that reducing this ratio has the effect of

favoring the general spread of intolerance and it does not offer any significant new finding for the present work.

Consistent with previous findings⁴², one observes that minorities are susceptible to intolerant outbreaks when they are under high economic stress ϵ_A (blue region in Figs. 3 and 4 for low values of y). But these figures also illustrate the effect of economic inequality. For a given composition of the population y , moving along the lines with constant $\epsilon = y\epsilon_A + (1-y)\epsilon_B$ in the ϵ_B - ϵ_A plane (grey lines in Figures 3 and 4) keeps constant the total population wealth while at the same time changes the Gini coefficient G —which will then be proportional to the difference $\epsilon_B - \epsilon_A$ according to Eq. 1. Above the diagonal $\epsilon_B = \epsilon_A$, $G < 0$ (A is disfavored), whereas below the diagonal $G > 0$ (A is favored).

The general trend is that egalitarian ($G = 0$) fully tolerant populations are able to repel intolerance become sensitive to its invasion by increasing inequality. On the other hand, a population for which intolerance can spread when $G = 0$ (blue region in Figs. 3 and 4) can be made intolerance-proof by introducing some economic inequality ($G \neq 0$) in favor of the group targeted by intolerance. This holds up to a certain level of global economic stress in the case of strategy **II** minorities; beyond that, intolerance invades regardless of the value of G .

Likewise, full tolerance can be restored in a population IT (red region of Figs. 3 and 4) by modifying G in favor of the intolerant minority that is susceptible to be invaded by tolerant individuals. In general, the lower the global economic stress the less inequality is needed for tolerance invasion to succeed. However this trend reverses if the intolerants constitute the majority; in this scenario the lower the global economic stress the more

inequality is needed to restore tolerance (and below a threshold tolerance can no longer be restored). Purple regions (overlaps of blue and red regions) are combinations of parameters for which I|TT and T|IT invasions can both occur. This means that neither TT or IT populations are stable, and the equilibrium will most likely consist of a mixture of tolerant and intolerant individuals in the same subpopulation. This effect can only be observed if the invaded population is a minority and if inequality favors them. In general, though, intolerance outbreaks will invade irreversibly.

Finally, Figs. 3 and 4 also show that, once intolerance has settled in one group, it is almost unavoidable that the whole population becomes completely intolerant regardless of the global economic stress and the Gini coefficient, especially if the intolerant group constitutes the majority. Thus, populations are at high risk of becoming fully intolerant in regions where I|TT and IT|I overlaps. If this happens there is no way back: A fully intolerant population can never be reverted to tolerance by changing the economic parameters.

C. Redistribution of wealth

The picture that has been presented shows that economic inequality can be an enhancer of intolerance, even more so than the global economic stress. Populations that would resist intolerance outbreaks can easily fall into intolerant attitudes if wealth is unequally distributed. It has already been shown that modifying inequality affects the ability of tolerance and intolerance to emerge, so then it makes sense to ask whether a redistribution of wealth can prevent intolerance from succeeding.

Assuming a fully tolerant population, we can gather together the areas where I|TT and TT|I invasions succeed, i.e., blue regions of Figs. 3 and 4 corresponding to y (subpopulation A) and $1-y$ (subpopulation B), and delimit a region of the plane $\epsilon_A-\epsilon_B$ where the population is intolerance-proof (*safe region*). This region is displayed in green in Figure 5. If the distribution of wealth in a population has a distribution within the safe region, tolerance is stable.

Redistributing wealth amounts to changing ϵ_A and ϵ_B along the line $y\epsilon_A + (1-y)\epsilon_B$ maintaining ϵ constant. A wealth redistribution policy can only be successful if this line crosses the safe region. Orange and yellow areas in Fig. 5 satisfy this condition. Outside those areas, redistributing wealth is an useless policy against outbreaks of intolerance. Nevertheless, the effect in these two areas is different.

Within the *late redistribution* region (orange in Fig. 5), an invasion I|TT can occur and transform the population into IT. However, full tolerance can be restored in one or two steps. First, reversing wealth inequality so as to bring the population into one of the zones where T|IT invasion is possible (red zones in Figs. 3 and 4). Second, once full tolerance is restored, and if the population is not

already in the safe region, wealth must be redistributed again to bring the population to the safe region.

On the other hand, within the *early redistribution* region (yellow in Fig. 5) wealth redistribution is only useful as a prevention policy: it has to be implemented *before* an intolerance outbreak takes place. Otherwise, since the population cannot be moved into one of the red zones of Figs. 3 and 4, once one of the groups becomes intolerant, chances are that the tolerant group eventually becomes intolerant as well (population falls in regions where IT|I or I|TI invasions can prosper). The only possibility to revert the population to TT is to move it into a region where T|IT (TI|T) and IT|I (I|TI) areas overlap. However, since both invasions can occur, there is no guarantee that the policy succeeds. If the population becomes completely intolerant, tolerance will never be restored even if the economic situation improves.

IV. DISCUSSION

The connection between global economic stress and outbursts of intolerance is well documented²⁶⁻³², and the present model of indirect reciprocity yields results in agreement with these observations. However, the aim of this work is to study the effect of economic inequality in the evolutionary emergence of intolerance. By letting subpopulations to undergo different levels of economic stress, inequality has been proved as a powerful enhancer of intolerance, making it easier for intolerant individuals to prosper even when global economic conditions are not too harsh. Additionally, discriminatory behaviors can easily escalate without the presence of new intolerant mutants. For instance, if the disfavored tolerant individuals constitute a majority, they withdraw their support from the wealthy intolerant minority simply by following their intrinsic strategy.

Results show how inequality and intolerance, despite having been defined as a type of out-group discrimination, have an important impact not only on attitudes against other group members but also toward their own kind. These behaviors are different for different evolutionarily stable strategies, revealing a diverse spectrum of possibilities to tackle intolerance under unequal populations. Some strategists intend to behave as cooperatively as possible with other tolerant individuals of their kind when they belong to the disfavored minority. This attitude can be interpreted as a sympathetic behavior that allows them to avoid the spread of bad reputations originated by their inability to cooperate when resources are scarce for them. In return, they pay the price of reducing their punishment capacity against individuals that have fairly acquired bad reputation. Other strategies, on the other hand, promote a more rigid behavior by never cooperating with individuals who have earned a bad reputation regardless of their own reputation and the disadvantaged conditions in which they may find themselves. However, it has the counterintuitive conse-

FIG. 5. Redistribution of wealth to prevent intolerance. Areas in the ϵ_A - ϵ_B plane, for different compositions of the population y and strategies **I** and **II**, where (i) intolerance cannot invade any of the subpopulations (*safe region*), (ii) a redistribution of the wealth can restore tolerance in the smallest subpopulation once intolerance has already invaded it (*late redistribution*), (iii) a redistribution of wealth before an outbreak of intolerance can take the whole population to the safe zone (*early and late redistribution*). Blue lines mark the boundaries for the success of the invasions I|TT and T|IT. Dotted lines correspond to $\epsilon_A = \epsilon_B$. Scenarios with $y > 0.5$ are equivalent to those shown with $y < 0.5$ by exchanging ϵ_A for ϵ_B , and y for $1 - y$. Benefit-to-cost ratio $b/c = 2$.

quence that disfavored individuals help more frequently to wealthier individuals, even if they display intolerant attitudes against them, than to those from their own kind when they are in minority. Some experiments have shown this kind of attitudes⁷⁰, at least when social identity is not shared⁷¹, which can propagate economic inequality. These differences among strategies bear some parallelism with the aspiration level of win-stay, lose-shift strategies in direct reciprocity^{72,73}: some donors display a lower aspiration level, cooperating not only when the recipient enjoys a good reputation, but also when both the recipient and herself own bad reputations, obtaining a good reputation in return; other donors hold higher aspiration levels and cooperate only if the recipient displays a good reputation. On the other hand, the capacity of individuals to punish bad behaviors is generally limited by their economic power. Under limited resources they are not able to efficiently implement, even when they intend to, different attitudes toward what they consider good and bad behaviors. It has been previously shown that the lack of resources, such as money or time, generally leads to poorer decisions due to the cognitive load imposed by

poverty⁷⁴. Despite the fact that intolerance outbreaks more easily in disfavored minorities, results have also shown that exceptionally a wealthy small minority within an unequal population can oscillate between tolerant and intolerant behaviors (or a mixed equilibrium of them).

The present study was able to delimit regions of inequality where intolerant behaviors cannot spread. More importantly, results have also shown regions where inequality is so high that it favors the appearance of intolerance, but where a proper redistribution of wealth may prevent that from happening. In order to become a viable solution, this redistribution has to fulfil two key requirements. First, it needs to favor equality: the emergence of intolerance can be avoided favoring the group that is susceptible of this invasion but if it is done at the expenses of increasing inequality, intolerance eventually may invade the disfavored group. Therefore, increasing inequality as a mean to avoid intolerance only has sense if the latter group owns specific features (external to the model) that make it resilience to intolerance. Secondly, the redistribution of wealth has to be applied *before* intolerance emerges. Otherwise it may not be as effective,

or even be plainly useless.

The model used in this work is affected by some simplifications to make the fundamental analysis feasible. For instance, the redistribution of wealth was implemented at no cost, and therefore, the results of the model are to be taken as the best-case scenario of what such a policy is able to achieve. There exist a number of other potential aspects beyond the scope of this work that could be studied increasing the level of complexity of the model⁷⁵: the impact of individuals' mobility across groups^{41,76–78}, the effect of a higher order reputation system⁷⁹, the importance of the quality of the information perceived in the private assessments⁸⁰, the possibility of signalling or communication⁸¹, the introduction of apology mechanisms⁸², the influence of different scales in finite size populations and network topologies^{83–85}. Handling these elements, together with other externalities such as the global economic power or the benefit-to-cost ratio, may help to limit the appearance of intolerance in situations where the redistribution of wealth alone is not enough.

The findings of this research are especially relevant given the rise of inequality in modern societies^{2,4–8} increasingly reliant on public reputation systems, which are not able to reduce initial inequalities⁸⁶. Moreover, the recent COVID-19 global pandemic has boosted the situation, leaving the most vulnerable groups in an even more precarious situation⁹. Inequality, without appropriate policies to curb it, escalates⁸⁷, and brings significant dangers^{88,89}: It is detrimental to the economy⁹⁰ and a source of socio-political instability^{91–94}, being a threat to democracy⁹⁵ and even the seed of civil wars⁹⁶. There exist clear indications that economic inequality has a direct connection with the emergence of intolerance in many current phenomena, such as Brexit or the rise of far-right populism^{97,98}, which strategically use problems derived from inequality to limit the redistribution of wealth and maintain a spiral of inequality⁹⁹. Other poli-

cies designed to directly protect the rights of minority groups (e.g., their distinctness) could yield the opposite effect they intend to, at least if economic inequality is preserved¹⁰⁰. On the other hand, experiments show that redistribution of wealth policies would be accepted by a significant part of society, especially if they are accompanied by a more clear perception of the existence of economic inequality^{101–103} and are fairly and efficiently implemented¹⁰⁴. All these evidences are consistent with the results of this work: the importance of implementing wealth redistribution policies before intolerance permeates part of the population.

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

Supplementary Figures represent the intention of cooperation as a function of the Gini coefficient for additional model parameter values.

AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

The author has no conflicts to disclose.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The author thanks José A. Cuesta and The Anh Han for helpful comments and suggestions. This work was supported by the Ministry of Science and Innovation (Spain) under the project PID2021-122711NB-C21.

Appendix: Reputation equilibria under different scenarios

As it was stated in the main text, the interactions with recipients of the same and of the opposite group, introduced in Eqs. 10–15, were split into $T_{i,j}^{\Lambda_l \Lambda_m}$ and $F_{i,j}^{\Lambda_l \Lambda_m}$, respectively. Fractions $T_{i,j}^{\Lambda_l \Lambda_m}$ are common for all invasion scenarios and can be obtained as

$$T_{i,A}^{\Lambda_A \Lambda_M} = \sum_{\alpha_A \alpha_M \beta_A \beta_M} x_i^{\alpha_A * \alpha_M} x_A^{\beta_A * \beta_M} Q^{\Lambda_A \Lambda_M}(\alpha_A \beta_A, \alpha_M \beta_M | \alpha_i \beta_i) \quad (\text{A.1})$$

$$T_{i,B}^{\Lambda_B \Lambda_M} = \sum_{\alpha_i \alpha_M \beta_B \beta_M} x_i^{* \alpha_B \alpha_B} x_B^{* \beta_B \beta_M} Q^{\Lambda_B \Lambda_M}(\alpha_B \beta_B, \alpha_M \beta_M | \alpha_i \beta_i) \quad (\text{A.2})$$

$$T_{i,i}^{\Lambda_A \Lambda_B} = \sum_{\alpha_A \alpha_B \beta_A \beta_B} x_i^{\alpha_A \alpha_B *} x_i^{\beta_A \beta_B *} Q^{\Lambda_A \Lambda_B}(\alpha_A \beta_A, \alpha_B \beta_B | \alpha_B \beta_B) \quad (\text{A.3})$$

$$Q^{\Lambda_l \Lambda_m}(\alpha_l \beta_l, \alpha_m \beta_m | \alpha_i \beta_i) = (1 - \epsilon_i) \delta(\Lambda_l, m_{\alpha_l \beta_l}(a_{\alpha_i \beta_i})) \delta(\Lambda_m, m_{\alpha_m \beta_m}(a_{\alpha_i \beta_i})) + \epsilon_i \delta(\Lambda_l, m_{\alpha_l \beta_l}(D)) \quad (\text{A.4})$$

where $Q^{\Lambda_l \Lambda_m}(\alpha_l \beta_l, \alpha_m \beta_m | \alpha_i \beta_i)$ is the probability that an i -type donor with reputation (α_i, β_i) acting on a recipient with reputation (β_l, β_m) , is assigned a reputation (Λ_l, Λ_m) by l -individuals and m -individuals. On the

other hand, fractions $F_{i,j}^{\Lambda_l \Lambda_m}$ depend on the specific scenario and are described in the following sections.

1. Auxiliary functions

Firstly, some auxiliary functions and the process to calculate reputations in homogeneous populations is presented. The main auxiliary function that will be used in the later mathematical process is

$$U(x_i, x_j) = \sum_{\alpha\beta} \chi_\alpha(x_i) \chi_\beta(x_j) R_i^{\alpha\beta}, \quad (\text{A.5})$$

where

$$R_i^{\alpha\beta} = (1 - \epsilon_i) m_{\alpha\beta}(a_{\alpha\beta}) + \epsilon_i m_{\alpha\beta}(D) \quad (\text{A.6})$$

represents the probability that a i -type donor with reputation α performing the action $a_{\alpha\beta}$ on a recipient with reputation β is considered good according to the moral assessment $m_{\alpha\beta}(a)$.

In a homogeneous population—where all its members belong to the same i -type—the dynamics of the fraction of good individuals g_i follows the differential equation

$$\frac{dg_i}{dt} = U(g_i, g_i) - g_i. \quad (\text{A.7})$$

In equilibrium $g_i = U(g_i, g_i)$, which is a quadratic equation with a unique stable solution $0 \leq g_i \leq 1$. A continuous perturbation of the above equation will be also consider:

$$x_i = rU(x_i, x_i) + 1 - r, \quad (\text{A.8})$$

and denote $x_i = p_i(r)$ its stable solution in the interval $[0, 1]$. The solution of the unperturbed equation is recovered with $p_i(1) = g_i$.

Another function that will be used is $q_i(r, s)$, which correspond to the solution of the linear equation $x_i = rU(x_i, s) + 1 - r$, $0 \leq r, s \leq 1$:

$$q_i(r, s) = \frac{1 + r [sR_i^{BG} + (1 - s)R_i^{BB} - 1]}{1 - r [sR_i^{GG} - (1 - s)R_i^{GB} + kP_{BG} + (1 - s)R_i^{BB}]}. \quad (\text{A.9})$$

2. I|TT scenario

Since residents do not distinguish classes, the resident population acts as a homogeneous population. Therefore $x_i^{*A\Lambda M} = x_i^{A*\Lambda M}$, $\eta_{B,A} = \eta_{A,B} = \eta_{A,A}$, $\eta_{B,M} = \eta_{A,M}$, and $\eta_{M,B} = 0$. The fraction of good residents is $g_A^A = p_A(1)$ and $g_B^A = p_B(1)$, and accordingly,

$$x_A^{G*B} = g_A^A - x_A^{G*G}, \quad (\text{A.10})$$

$$x_A^{B*G} = 1 - g_A^A - x_A^{B*B}. \quad (\text{A.11})$$

Therefore the fraction $F_{A,B}^{A\Lambda M}$ introduced in Eq. 10 can be expressed in this scenario as

$$F_{A,B}^{A\Lambda M} = \sum_{\alpha\beta} \chi_\alpha(g_A^A) \chi_\beta(g_B^A) P_A^{A\Lambda M}(\alpha\beta), \quad (\text{A.12})$$

$$P_A^{A\Lambda M}(\alpha\beta) = (1 - \epsilon_A) \delta(\Lambda_A, m_{\alpha\beta}(a_{\alpha\beta})) \delta(\Lambda_M, \tilde{a}_{\alpha\beta}) + \epsilon_A \delta(\Lambda_A, m_{\alpha\beta}(D)) \delta(\Lambda_M, G), \quad (\text{A.13})$$

where $\tilde{a}_{\alpha\beta}$ stands for the opposite action to $a_{\alpha\beta}$. Once we numerically solve the two Eqs. 10, Eq. 14, which corresponds to the intolerant mutants, can be solved analytically by taking into account that

$$F_{M,B}^{A\Lambda M} = \sum_{\alpha\beta} \chi_\alpha(g_M^A) \chi_\beta(g_B^A) P_M^{A\Lambda M}(\alpha\beta), \quad (\text{A.14})$$

$$P_M^{A\Lambda M}(\alpha\beta) = \delta(\Lambda_A, m_{\alpha\beta}(D)) \delta(\Lambda_M, G). \quad (\text{A.15})$$

If at equilibrium, Eq. 14 is summed over Λ_A and g_M^M is given by $q_A(g_A^M, y)$. Then the set of Eqs. 14 reduces to just two equations.

3. T|IT scenario

Since mutants and B-residents are both tolerant, they will judge every player equally and then $x_i^{A\Lambda B*} = x_i^{A*\Lambda M}$. On the other hand, A-residents are intolerant ($\eta_{A,B} = 0$) and their dynamics is described by Eq. 10, where

$$F_{A,B}^{A\Lambda M} = \sum_{\alpha\beta} \chi_\alpha(g_A^M) \chi_\beta(g_B^M) P_A^{A\Lambda M}(\alpha\beta), \quad (\text{A.16})$$

$$P_A^{A\Lambda M}(\alpha\beta) = \delta(\Lambda_M, m_{\alpha\beta}(D)) \delta(\Lambda_A, G). \quad (\text{A.17})$$

Summing Eq. 10 over Λ_M in equilibrium one obtains that $g_A^A = p_A(y)$. In this scenario it is also necessary to calculate g_B^M . Since B -mutant's judgements are the same as those of B -residents, g_B^M is given at equilibrium by

$$g_B^M = (1 - y)U(g_B^M, g_B^M) + yU(g_B^M, g_A^M). \quad (\text{A.18})$$

Therefore, a system of three equations—two from Eqs. 10 plus Eq. A.18—needs to be solved numerically. After that, the set of Eqs. 14 with

$$F_{M,B}^{A\Lambda M} = \sum_{\alpha\beta} \chi_\alpha(g_M^M) \chi_\beta(g_B^M) P_M^{A\Lambda M}(\alpha\beta), \quad (\text{A.19})$$

$$P_M^{A\Lambda M}(\alpha\beta) = (1 - \epsilon_A) \delta(\Lambda_M, m_{\alpha\beta}(a_{\alpha\beta})) \delta(\Lambda_A, \tilde{a}_{\alpha\beta}) + \epsilon_A \delta(\Lambda_M, m_{\alpha\beta}(D)) \delta(\Lambda_A, G), \quad (\text{A.20})$$

can be solved analytically, taking into account that summing over Λ_A at equilibrium yields $g_M^M = q_A(yg_A^M + (1 - y)g_B^M, 1)$.

4. IT|I scenario

In this scenario, mutants belongs to subpopulation B and intolerant toward A-residents, who are intolerant toward B-type individuals. Hence $\eta_{A,B} = \eta_{A,M} = \eta_{M,A} = 0$.

In order to calculate g_A^B we first need to compute $x_A^{A\Lambda B*}$ through Eq. 11, where

$$F_{A,B}^{A\Lambda B} = \sum_{\alpha\beta} \chi_\alpha(g_A^B) \chi_\beta(g_B^B) P_A^{A\Lambda B}(\alpha\beta), \quad (\text{A.21})$$

$$P_A^{A\Lambda B}(\alpha\beta) = \delta(\Lambda_B, m_{\alpha\beta}(D)) \delta(\Lambda_A, G), \quad (\text{A.22})$$

and summing over Λ_B at equilibrium one obtains that $g_A^A = p_A(y)$. In this way, we reduced the set of Eq. 11 to just two equations.

On the other hand, the dynamics of the tolerant individuals is given by Eq. 13, with

$$F_{B,A}^{\Lambda_B \Lambda_M} = \sum_{\alpha\beta} \chi_\alpha(g_B^B) \chi_\beta(g_A^B) P_B^{\Lambda_B \Lambda_M}(\alpha\beta), \quad (\text{A.23})$$

$$P_B^{\Lambda_B \Lambda_M}(\alpha\beta) = (1 - \epsilon_B) \delta(\Lambda_B, m_{\alpha\beta}(a_{\alpha\beta})) \delta(\Lambda_M, \tilde{a}_{\alpha\beta}) + \epsilon_B \delta(\Lambda_B, m_{\alpha\beta}(D)) \delta(\Lambda_M, G). \quad (\text{A.24})$$

Taking into account that $x_B^{*AG} = 1 - x_B^{*GG} - x_B^{*GB} - x_B^{*BB}$, five coupled equations needs to be solved, namely, three from Eqs. 10 and two from Eqs. 12.

The dynamics of the mutants is solved from Eq. 15, where

$$F_{M,A}^{\Lambda_B \Lambda_M} = \sum_{\alpha\beta} \chi_\alpha(g_M^B) \chi_\beta(g_A^B) P_M^{\Lambda_B \Lambda_M}(\alpha\beta), \quad (\text{A.25})$$

$$P_M^{\Lambda_B \Lambda_M}(\alpha\beta) = \delta(\Lambda_B, m_{\alpha\beta}(D)) \delta(\Lambda_M, G). \quad (\text{A.26})$$

Summing over Λ_B at equilibrium yields $g_M^M = q_B(g_B^M, 1 - y)$, and reduced the last set of equations to only two linear.

5. T|II scenario

In this last scenario a small fraction of tolerant mutants, who belong to subpopulation A, tries to invade a completely intolerant population. Therefore $\eta_{A,B} = \eta_{B,A} = \eta_{B,M} = 0$. Similar analysis can be done for B-type mutants and I|TI invasion exchanging A for B and y for $1 - y$.

The dynamics for the intolerant A-residents is described by Eq. 10 with

$$F_{A,B}^{\Lambda_A \Lambda_M} = \sum_{\alpha\beta} \chi_\alpha(g_A^M) \chi_\beta(g_B^M) P_A^{\Lambda_A \Lambda_M}(\alpha\beta), \quad (\text{A.27})$$

$$P_A^{\Lambda_A \Lambda_M}(\alpha\beta) = \delta(\Lambda_M, m_{\alpha\beta}(D)) \delta(\Lambda_A, G). \quad (\text{A.28})$$

Summing over Λ_M at equilibrium yields $g_A^A = p(y)$.

Computing first $x_B^{* \Lambda_B \Lambda_M}$ is necessary in order to calculate g_B^M . Equation 13 describes the dynamics for these fractions, where

$$F_{B,A}^{\Lambda_B \Lambda_M} = \sum_{\alpha\beta} \chi_\alpha(g_B^M) \chi_\beta(g_A^M) P_B^{\Lambda_B \Lambda_M}(\alpha\beta), \quad (\text{A.29})$$

$$P_B^{\Lambda_B \Lambda_M}(\alpha\beta) = \delta(\Lambda_M, m_{\alpha\beta}(D)) \delta(\Lambda_B, G), \quad (\text{A.30})$$

and summing again over Λ_M one obtains that $g_B^B = p(1 - y)$. The four resulting coupled equations —two from Eqs. 12 and two from Eq. 13— need to be solved numerically.

On the other hand, the dynamics of the tolerant mutants is given by Eq. 13, where

$$F_{M,B}^{\Lambda_A \Lambda_M} = \sum_{\alpha\beta} \chi_\alpha(g_M^M) \chi_\beta(g_B^M) P_M^{\Lambda_A \Lambda_M}(\alpha\beta), \quad (\text{A.31})$$

$$P_M^{\Lambda_A \Lambda_M}(\alpha\beta) = (1 - \epsilon_A) \delta(\Lambda_M, m_{\alpha\beta}(a_{\alpha\beta})) \delta(\Lambda_A, \tilde{a}_{\alpha\beta}) + \epsilon_A \delta(\Lambda_M, m_{\alpha\beta}(D)) \delta(\Lambda_A, G). \quad (\text{A.32})$$

This set of equations can be reduced to just two because summing over Λ_A at equilibrium yields $g_M^M = q_i(yg_A^M + (1 - y)g_B^M, 1)$.

¹S. M. Mattison, E. A. Smith, M. K. Shenk, and E. E. Cochrane, “The evolution of inequality,” *Evolutionary Anthropology: Issues, News, and Reviews* **25**, 184–199 (2016).

²F. Alvaredo, *The World Inequality Report: 2018* (Harvard University Press, 2018).

³J. Mazur, “Labor’s new internationalism,” *Foreign Aff.* **79**, 79 (2000).

⁴G. Firebaugh, “The trend in between-nation income inequality,” *Annual Review of Sociology*, 323–339 (2000).

⁵B. Goesling, “Changing income inequalities within and between nations: New evidence,” *American Sociological Review*, 745–761 (2001).

⁶C. S. Fischer and M. Hout, *Century of difference: How America changed in the last one hundred years* (Russell Sage Foundation, 2006).

⁷T. Piketty, E. Saez, and G. Zucman, “Distributional national accounts: methods and estimates for the united states,” *The Quarterly Journal of Economics* **133**, 553–609 (2018).

⁸T. Blanchet, L. Chancel, A. Gethin, *et al.*, “How unequal is europe? evidence from distributional national accounts, 1980–2017,” *WID. World working paper* **6** (2019).

⁹L. Chancel, T. Piketty, E. Saez, and G. Zucman, “World inequality report 2022,” *World Inequality Lab* (2021).

¹⁰W. G. Sumner, “Folways,” Boston. Ginn (1906).

¹¹R. A. LeVine and D. T. Campbell, “Ethnocentrism,” New York: John Wiley (1972).

¹²L. A. Hirschfeld, “Race in the making,” Cambridge, MA: MIT Press (1996).

¹³H. Bernhard, U. Fischbacher, and E. Fehr, “Parochial altruism in humans,” *Nature* **442**, 912–915 (2006).

¹⁴N. Struch and S. H. Schwartz, “Intergroup aggression: Its predictors and distinctness from in-group bias,” *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology* **56**, 346–373 (1989).

¹⁵G. Allport, *The nature of prejudice* (Addison-Wesley, 1954).

¹⁶S. T. Fiske, “Stereotyping, prejudice, and discrimination at the seam between the centuries: Evolution, culture, mind, and brain,” *European Journal of Social Psychology* **30**, 299–322 (2000).

¹⁷S. T. Fiske, “What we know now about bias and intergroup conflict, the problem of the century,” *Current Directions in Psychological Science* **11**, 123–128 (2002).

¹⁸T. Yamagishi, N. Jin, and T. Kiyonari, “Bounded generalized reciprocity: Ingroup boasting and ingroup favoritism,” *Advances in group processes* **16**, 161–197 (1999).

¹⁹F. Fu, C. E. Tarnita, N. A. Christakis, L. Wang, D. G. Rand, and M. A. Nowak, “Evolution of in-group favoritism,” *Scientific reports* **2**, 1–6 (2012).

²⁰D. Balliet, J. Wu, and C. K. De Dreu, “Ingroup favoritism in cooperation: a meta-analysis,” *Psychological bulletin* **140**, 1556 (2014).

²¹J. J. Ray and F. H. Lovejoy, “The generality of racial prejudice,” *Journal of Social Psychology* **126**, 563–564 (1986).

²²E. Palmore, *Ageism: Negative and positive* (Springer Publishing Company, 1999).

²³E. Cashdan, “Ethnocentrism and xenophobia: A cross-cultural study,” *Current Anthropology* **42**, 760–765 (2001).

²⁴M. Bertrand and E. Duflo, “Field experiments on discrimination,” *Handbook of economic field experiments* **1**, 309–393 (2017).

²⁵N. Ellemers *et al.*, “Gender stereotypes,” *Annual review of psychology* **69**, 275–298 (2018).

²⁶J. Dollard, N. E. Miller, L. W. Doob, O. H. Mowrer, and R. R. Sears, *Frustration and Aggression* (Yale University Press, New Haven, Connecticut, 1939).

²⁷C. I. Hovland and R. S. Sears, “Minor studies of aggression vi:

- Correlation of lynchings with economic indices," *J. Psych.* **9**, 301–310 (1940).
- ²⁸S. M. Lipset, "Democracy and working-class authoritarianism," *American Sociological Review*, 482–501 (1959).
- ²⁹J. Levin and W. C. Levin, *The Functions of Discrimination and Prejudice* (Harper and Row, New York, 1982).
- ³⁰C. H. Persell, A. Green, and L. Gurevich, "Civil society, economic distress, and social tolerance," in *Sociological forum*, Vol. 16 (Springer, 2001) pp. 203–230.
- ³¹J. L. Gibson, "Becoming Tolerant? Short-Term Changes in Russian Political Culture," *Brit. J. Pol. Sci.* **32**, 309–333 (2002).
- ³²S. Svallfors, *The moral economy of class: Class and attitudes in comparative perspective* (Stanford University Press, 2006).
- ³³S. Knack and P. Keefer, "Does social capital have an economic payoff? a cross-country investigation," *The Quarterly journal of economics* **112**, 1251–1288 (1997).
- ³⁴E. M. Uslaner, *The Moral Foundations of Trust* (Cambridge University Press, 2002).
- ³⁵R. Andersen and T. Fetner, "Economic inequality and intolerance: Attitudes toward homosexuality in 35 democracies," *American Journal of Political Science* **52**, 942–958 (2008).
- ³⁶R. Andersen and J. Curtis, "The polarizing effect of economic inequality on class identification: Evidence from 44 countries," *Research in Social Stratification and Mobility* **30**, 129–141 (2012).
- ³⁷T. Nhim, A. Richter, and X. Zhu, "The resilience of social norms of cooperation under resource scarcity and inequality—an agent-based model on sharing water over two harvesting seasons," *Ecological Complexity* **40**, 100709 (2019).
- ³⁸N. Masuda, "Ingroup favoritism and intergroup cooperation under indirect reciprocity based on group reputation," *J. Theor. Biol.* **311**, 8–18 (2012).
- ³⁹M. Nakamura and N. Masuda, "Groupwise information sharing promotes ingroup favoritism in indirect reciprocity," *BMC Evol. Biol.* **12**, 213 (2012).
- ⁴⁰K. Oishi, T. Shimad, and N. Ito, "Group formation through indirect reciprocity," *Phys. Rev. E* **87**, 030801 (2013).
- ⁴¹R. M. Whitaker, G. B. Colombo, and D. G. Rand, "Indirect reciprocity and the evolution of prejudicial groups," *Scientific reports* **8**, 1–14 (2018).
- ⁴²L. A. Martinez-Vaquero and J. A. Cuesta, "Spreading of intolerance under economic stress: Results from a reputation-based model," *Phys. Rev. E* **90**, 022805 (2014).
- ⁴³R. Sugden, *The economics of rights, co-operation and welfare* (Basil Blackwell, Oxford, 1986).
- ⁴⁴R. D. Alexander, *The Biology of Moral Systems* (New York: Aldine de Gruyter, 1987).
- ⁴⁵M. A. Nowak and K. Sigmund, "Evolution of indirect reciprocity by image scoring," *Nature* **393**, 573–577 (1998).
- ⁴⁶R. Boyd and P. J. Richerson, "The evolution of indirect reciprocity," *Social networks* **11**, 213–236 (1989).
- ⁴⁷O. Leimar and P. Hammerstein, "Evolution of cooperation through indirect reciprocity," *Proc. R. Soc. Lond. B* **268**, 745–753 (2001).
- ⁴⁸K. Panchanathan and R. Boyd, "A tale of two defectors: the importance of standing for evolution of indirect reciprocity," *J. Theor. Biol.* **224**, 115–126 (2003).
- ⁴⁹M. A. Nowak and K. Sigmund, "Evolution of indirect reciprocity," *Nature* **437**, 1291–1298 (2005).
- ⁵⁰M. A. Nowak, "Five rules for the evolution of cooperation," *Science* **314**, 1560–1563 (2006).
- ⁵¹M. Dufwenberg, U. Gneezy, W. Güth, and E. van Demme, "Direct vs indirect reciprocity: An experiment," *Homo Oecon* **18**, 19–30 (2001).
- ⁵²M. Milinski, D. Semmann, and H.-J. Krambeck, "Reputation helps solve the tragedy of the commons," *Nature* **415**, 424–426 (2002).
- ⁵³K. Panchanathan and R. Boyd, "Indirect reciprocity can stabilise cooperation without the second-order free-rider problem," *Nature* **432**, 499–205 (2004).
- ⁵⁴D. Semmann, H.-J. Krambeck, and M. Milinski, "Strategic investment in reputation," *J. Behav. Ecol. Sociobiol.* **56**, 248–252 (2004).
- ⁵⁵S. Suzuki and E. Akiyama, "Evolution of indirect reciprocity in groups of various sizes and comparison with direct reciprocity," *J. Theor. Biol.* **245**, 539–552 (2007).
- ⁵⁶E. Yoeli, M. Hoffman, D. G. Rand, and M. A. Nowak, "Powering up with indirect reciprocity in a large-scale field experiment," *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* **110**, 10424–10429 (2013).
- ⁵⁷R. L. Trivers, "The evolution of reciprocal altruism," *Q. Rev. Biol.* **46**, 35–57 (1971).
- ⁵⁸M. A. Nowak and S. Roch, "Upstream reciprocity and the evolution of gratitude," *Proc. R. Soc. B* **274**, 605–610 (2007).
- ⁵⁹H. Ohtsuki and Y. Iwasa, "How should we define goodness?—reputation dynamics in indirect reciprocity," *J. Theor. Biol.* **231**, 107–120 (2004).
- ⁶⁰H. Brandt and K. Sigmund, "The logic of reprobation: assessment and action rules for indirect reciprocation," *J. Theor. Biol.* **231**, 475–486 (2004).
- ⁶¹E. Fehr, "Don't lose your reputation," *Nature* **432**, 449–450 (2004).
- ⁶²H. Ohtsuki and Y. Iwasa, "The leading eight: Social norms that can maintain cooperation by indirect reciprocity," *J. Theor. Biol.* **239**, 435–444 (2006).
- ⁶³L. A. Martinez-Vaquero and J. A. Cuesta, "Evolutionary stability and resistance to cheating in an indirect reciprocity model based on reputation," *Phys. Rev. E* **87**, 052810 (2013).
- ⁶⁴G. E. Bolton, E. Katok, and A. Ockenfels, "How effective are electronic reputation mechanisms? an experimental investigation," *Management science* **50**, 1587–1602 (2004).
- ⁶⁵A. Jøsang, R. Ismail, and C. Boyd, "A survey of trust and reputation systems for online service provision," *Decision support systems* **43**, 618–644 (2007).
- ⁶⁶M. A. Fishman, "Indirect reciprocity among imperfect individuals," *J. Theor. Biol.* **225**, 285–292 (2003).
- ⁶⁷A. Lotem, M. A. Fishman, and L. Stone, "Evolution of cooperation between individuals," *Nature* **400**, 226–227 (1999).
- ⁶⁸C. Gini, "On the measure of concentration with special reference to income and statistics," *Colorado College Publication, General Series* **208**, 73–79 (1936).
- ⁶⁹J. Smith and G. R. Price, "The logic of animal conflict," *Nature* **246**, 15–18 (1973).
- ⁷⁰L. M. Hackel and J. Zaki, "Propagation of economic inequality through reciprocity and reputation," *Psychological science* **29**, 604–613 (2018).
- ⁷¹L. Gangadharan, P. J. Grossman, M. K. Molle, and J. Vecchi, "Impact of social identity and inequality on antisocial behaviour," *European Economic Review* **119**, 199–215 (2019).
- ⁷²M. A. Nowak, K. Sigmund, and E. El-Sedy, "Automata, repeated games and noise," *J. Math. Biol.* **33**, 703–722 (1995).
- ⁷³L. A. Martinez-Vaquero, J. A. Cuesta, and A. Sánchez, "Generosity pays in the presence of direct reciprocity: A comprehensive study of 2×2 repeated games," *PLoS ONE* **7**, e35135 (2012).
- ⁷⁴A. Mani, S. Mullainathan, E. Shafir, and J. Zhao, "Poverty impedes cognitive function," *science* **341**, 976–980 (2013).
- ⁷⁵F. P. Santos, J. M. Pacheco, and F. C. Santos, "The complexity of human cooperation under indirect reciprocity," *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B* **376**, 20200291 (2021).
- ⁷⁶F. Fu, C. E. Tarnita, N. A. Christakis, L. Wang, D. G. Rand, and M. A. Nowak, "Evolution of in-group favoritism," *Sci Rep.* **2**, 460 (2012).
- ⁷⁷L. Zhang, C. Huang, H. Li, Q. Dai, and J. Yang, "Effects of directional migration for pursuit of profitable circumstances in evolutionary games," *Chaos, Solitons & Fractals* **144**, 110709 (2021).
- ⁷⁸M. Oliveira, F. Karimi, M. Zens, J. Schaible, M. Géniois, and M. Strohmaier, "Group mixing drives inequality in face-to-face gatherings," *Communications Physics* **5**, 1–9 (2022).

- ⁷⁹Y. Murase, M. Kim, and S. K. Baek, "Social norms in indirect reciprocity with ternary reputations," *Scientific Reports* **12**, 1–15 (2022).
- ⁸⁰C. Hilbe, L. Schmid, J. Tkadlec, K. Chatterjee, and M. A. Nowak, "Indirect reciprocity with private, noisy, and incomplete information," *Proceedings of the national academy of sciences* **115**, 12241–12246 (2018).
- ⁸¹L. A. Martinez-Vaquero, F. C. Santos, and V. Trianni, "Signalling boosts the evolution of cooperation in repeated group interactions," *Journal of the Royal Society Interface* **17**, 20200635 (2020).
- ⁸²L. A. Martinez-Vaquero, T. A. Han, L. M. Pereira, and T. Lenaerts, "Apology and forgiveness evolve to resolve failures in cooperative agreements," *Scientific reports* **5**, 1–12 (2015).
- ⁸³F. Karimi, M. Génois, C. Wagner, P. Singer, and M. Strohmaier, "Homophily influences ranking of minorities in social networks," *Scientific reports* **8**, 1–12 (2018).
- ⁸⁴Z. Hu, X. Li, J. Wang, C. Xia, Z. Wang, and M. Perc, "Adaptive reputation promotes trust in social networks," *IEEE Transactions on Network Science and Engineering* **8**, 3087–3098 (2021).
- ⁸⁵P. DiMaggio and F. Garip, "Network effects and social inequality," *Annual review of sociology* (2012).
- ⁸⁶J. Kas, R. Corten, and A. van de Rijt, "The role of reputation systems in digital discrimination," *Socio-economic review* **20**, 1905–1932 (2022).
- ⁸⁷A. S. Browman, M. Destin, M. S. Kearney, and P. B. Levine, "How economic inequality shapes mobility expectations and behaviour in disadvantaged youth," *Nature Human Behaviour* **3**, 214–220 (2019).
- ⁸⁸J. Jetten, Z. Wang, N. K. Steffens, F. Mols, K. Peters, and M. Verkuyten, "A social identity analysis of responses to economic inequality," *Current Opinion in Psychology* **18**, 1–5 (2017).
- ⁸⁹J. Jetten and K. Peters, *The social psychology of inequality* (Springer, 2019).
- ⁹⁰S. Bowles, C. M. Fong, H. Gintis, and U. Pagano, *The new economics of inequality and redistribution* (Cambridge University Press, 2012).
- ⁹¹B. M. Russett, "Inequality and instability: The relation of land tenure to politics," *World Politics* **16**, 442–454 (1964).
- ⁹²S. P. Huntington, *Political order in changing societies* (Yale University Press, 1968).
- ⁹³A. Alesina and R. Perotti, "Income distribution, political instability, and investment," *European economic review* **40**, 1203–1228 (1996).
- ⁹⁴R. Perotti, "Growth, income distribution, and democracy: What the data say," *Journal of Economic growth* **1**, 149–187 (1996).
- ⁹⁵R. Andersen, "Support for democracy in cross-national perspective: The detrimental effect of economic inequality," *Research in Social Stratification and Mobility* **30**, 389–402 (2012).
- ⁹⁶L.-E. Cederman, K. S. Gleditsch, and H. Buhaug, *Inequality, grievances, and civil war* (Cambridge University Press, 2013).
- ⁹⁷R. F. Inglehart and P. Norris, "Trump, brexit, and the rise of populism: Economic have-nots and cultural backlash," HKS Working paper no. RWP16-026 (2016).
- ⁹⁸R. Meleady, C. R. Seger, and M. Vermue, "Examining the role of positive and negative intergroup contact and anti-immigrant prejudice in brexit," *British Journal of Social Psychology* **56**, 799–808 (2017).
- ⁹⁹S. Jay, A. Batruch, J. Jetten, C. McGarty, and O. T. Muldoon, "Economic inequality and the rise of far-right populism: A social psychological analysis," *Journal of Community & Applied Social Psychology* **29**, 418–428 (2019).
- ¹⁰⁰P. M. Sniderman and L. Hagendoorn, "When ways of life collide," in *When Ways of Life Collide* (Princeton University Press, 2009).
- ¹⁰¹J. D. García-Castro, R. Rodríguez-Bailón, and G. B. Willis, "Perceiving economic inequality in everyday life decreases tolerance to inequality," *Journal of Experimental Social Psychology* **90**, 104019 (2020).
- ¹⁰²C. Chisadza, N. Nicholls, and E. Yitbarek, "Group identity in fairness decisions: Discrimination or inequality aversion?" *Journal of Behavioral and Experimental Economics* **93**, 101722 (2021).
- ¹⁰³K. Kirkland, J. Jetten, M. Wilks, and M. Nielsen, "How economic inequality affects prosocial behavior in children across development," *Journal of Experimental Child Psychology* **210**, 105202 (2021).
- ¹⁰⁴R. Koster, J. Balaguer, A. Tacchetti, A. Weinstein, T. Zhu, O. Hauser, D. Williams, L. Campbell-Gillingham, P. Thacker, M. Botvinick, *et al.*, "Human-centered mechanism design with democratic AI," *Nature Human Behaviour* (2022).

This is the author's peer reviewed, accepted manuscript. However, the online version of record will be different from this version once it has been copyedited and typeset.
PLEASE CITE THIS ARTICLE AS DOI: 10.1063/5.0135376

Intention of cooperation

Strategy I

Strategy II

This is the author's peer reviewed, accepted manuscript. However, the online version of record will be different from this version once it has been copyedited and typeset.
PLEASE CITE THIS ARTICLE AS DOI: 10.1063/5.0135332

This is the author's peer reviewed, accepted manuscript. However, the online version of record will be different from this version once it has been copyedited and proofread.
PLEASE CITE THIS ARTICLE AS DOI: 10.1063/5.0135332

This is the author's peer reviewed, accepted manuscript. However, the online version of record will be different from this version once it has been fully edited and proof corrected. It is subject to change without notice. This version is for Strategy I only. Strategy II is version once it has been fully edited and proof corrected. Please cite this article as DOI: 10.1063/5.01355376

